

OBJECT DETECTION ON DIGITAL PATHOLOGY SLIDES
for unsupervised morphology discovery

BACHELOR'S THESIS

Botond Koroknai
Physics BSC III.

Thesis supervisors:

Dr. István Csabai
Professor

Eötvös Loránd University Faculty of Natural Sciences
Department of Physics of Complex Systems

Alex Olar
PhD student

Eötvös Loránd University Faculty of Informatics

Eötvös Loránd University
Institute of Physics
Department of Physics of Complex Systems
2024. May, Budapest

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Methods	4
2.1	Dimensionality reduction	4
2.1.1	PCA	4
2.1.2	t-SNE	5
2.1.3	UMAP	6
2.2	Clustering	7
2.3	Evaluation	7
2.3.1	Free response Receiver Operating Characteristic	8
2.4	Detection algorithms	9
2.4.1	R-CNN	10
2.4.2	Fast R-CNN	12
2.4.3	Faster R-CNN	12
2.4.4	Segmentation	13
3	Results	14
3.1	Dataset	14
3.2	FROC	16
3.2.1	The cost matrix	16
3.2.2	Hungarian matching	16
3.2.3	The statistics	17
3.2.4	Implementing my own FROC curve plotting function	18
3.2.5	The comparison between my function and the package	20
3.3	Detection algorithms	22
3.3.1	Detection of cells	22
3.3.2	Segmentation of cells	26
4	Summary	30
5	Acknowledgements	30

Abstract

Astrocytes play a key role in the healthy functioning of the central nervous system, and their morphological disorders are theoretically linked to the development of various neurological diseases, such as Alzheimer's or Parkinson's. This thesis aims to present a comprehensive study on the clustering of astrocytes to identify morphological differences among them.

Several different techniques were used to cluster the astrocytes. These include primitive ones, like clustering the cells as images, and complex ones to capture the real complexity and variability in their shapes. The complex methods use tools such as Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs) for cell detection and segmentation to reveal their detailed morphological features. Using these precise segmentation masks, two different cell representations were developed (contour interpolation and ellipse fitting) to create unified dataset of astrocytes for clustering.

Another key part of the thesis was dedicated to developing a custom Free-Response Receiver Operating Characteristic (FROC) curve plotting function, as well as the upgrade of the coco-froc analysis package (Olar, Koroknai, 2024)[18], which was essential for evaluating and visualizing the performance of the detection models, providing a comprehensive metric that highlights the sensitivity and false positive rates across different confidence thresholds.

1 Introduction

Recent improvements in computer vision have had a transformative effect on several scientific disciplines. One of the most significant impacts has been in medical research and diagnostics. With the help of computer algorithms, medical professionals can now interpret medical images with previously unachievable accuracy, identifying microscopic abnormalities and patterns that may have been missed before.

My work in this large discipline of medical imaging is related to the detection and clustering of glial cells, with a particular focus on a subset of them known as astrocytes. Astrocytes are an important component of the overall architecture of the central nervous system (CNS) and play a key role in providing a variety of essential support functions that are critical for synaptic activity. These star-shaped cells, appropriately named for their distinctive morphology similar to astronomical bodies, extend their activities to modulate neurotransmitter levels, regulate synaptic transmission, and maintain the fragile homeostasis of the CNS microenvironment. In addition, these diverse cells serve as guardians of neuronal health by responding rapidly to pathological insults and oxidative stress. (Sofroniew, Vinters, 2010)[24]. Understanding the role of these cells is crucial because their morphological abnormalities have been implicated in various diseases, such as Alzheimer's or Parkinson's (Suleymanova, et al. , 2018). [25].

To investigate the cells, they need to be located, which is usually a long process of staining the tissues, digitalizing them, and counting the astrocytes manually. The use of image processing and deep convolutional neural networks (DCNN) should speed up this process by orders of magnitude, not to mention that it may make fewer errors than manually locating and counting cells.

Once the astrocytes are located within the tissues, the investigation of the cellular disorders can begin. In this study, the goal was to present the clustering of these detected cells with the help of several different methods of dimension-reduced visualization, like t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE), uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP), principal component analysis (PCA), and clustering techniques such as the density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN). The intention was to show that these newly created dimensionally-reduced datasets would reveal complex patterns of spatial density variations and morphological irregularities. Thus by separating the cells, a basis for further in-depth analysis could be created.

The dataset used for the research (Olar, et al., 2024) [19] consists of high-resolution microscopy images of human brain tissues obtained from eight different patients. The tissues were stained with aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member L1 (ALDH1L1) and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP). With the help of staining techniques, key components can be illuminated, to help identify, localize, and quantify them. In the case of brain tissue, stain-

ing allows the visualization and characterization of different cell types, thus revealing their organization and morphology.

Since the annotation of the cells plays an important part in training detection models, it was done by experts, ensuring a reliable ground truth that reflects the consensus of multiple annotators. To ease its computational processing, the annotations were organized into a Common Objects in Context (COCO) (Lin, et al., 2014)[15] format, which is commonly used for detection datasets such as this. The intention was to train a few different DCNN detection models on this dataset and compare their performance with each other on designated test images. The building and fine-tuning of these detection models was done using the Detectron 2 framework (Wu, et al., 2019)[28]. By working with these models, the goal was to gain deeper insights into the details of neural network architectures and their effectiveness in accurately detecting and classifying astrocytes in complex biological images.

As for the evaluation of these detection models, one of the most common methods used is the calculation of the Free Response Receiver Operating Characteristics (FROC), which allows the creation of a curve that shows the accuracy of the model with respect to the errors it makes at a wide range of thresholds. Another popular way to measure performance is to calculate the mean average precision (mAP), which tells us the average precision of detection across multiple classes by generating the precision-recall curves for each class and calculating the area under them.

In summary, to ensure proper evaluation of the detection algorithms, it is essential to validate their effectiveness and reliability. This can be achieved by using diverse and representative datasets that reflect the variability and complexity of real-world scenarios. Also, the ground truth annotations must be accurate and consistent, which requires experts. In terms of evaluation, the use of multiple evaluation metrics, such as precision-recall curves, FROC curves, and mean average precision, provides a comprehensive understanding of algorithm performance from different perspectives.

It is worth mentioning that regardless of the widespread interest in this topic among researchers, there is a very limited number of pre-written and fully functional algorithms exist that are specifically designed for this task, which highlights the importance of developing reliable evaluation algorithms for object detection.

During my work, the evaluation of the models was done with the help of the coco-froc-analysis Python package (Olar, Koroknai, 2024) [18]. To validate the functionality and reliability of the package, another primitive FROC curve-generating function was written. By comparing the results from both the package and my own implementation, the correct functioning of the package could be verified, and it was also helpful to gain a deeper insight into the logic that is required to evaluate such detections.

To ensure that the finer details of the detected cells are captured for their clustering, they

were segmented using the Segment Anything package (Kirilov,et al.,2023)[13]. With the help of these segmentation masks, two different methods were created to represent the cells while preserving the most information about their morphology.

2 Methods

2.1 Dimensionality reduction

Dimensionality reduction techniques are important for simplifying complex data sets by reducing the number of features while preserving essential information. These methods, ranging from linear to nonlinear approaches, can help to improve computational efficiency and facilitate better visualization and interpretation of data.

The creation of the new dimensionally reduced datasets was done by the following three methods:

2.1.1 PCA

The intuition behind PCA (Pearson, 1901)[20] is to find the directions in the data where the variance is maximal. To give an example, if we think of our data set as a cloud of points in a high-dimensional space, then PCA aims to identify the axes along which this cloud stretches the most. These axes are the principal components, representing the most important trends or patterns in the data. By transforming the original features into this new set of orthogonal principal components, the data's dimensionality is reduced while retaining as much information as possible.

The first step of performing PCA is the standardization of the data:

$$x_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - \mu_j}{\sigma_j} \quad (1)$$

where x_{ij} is the standardized value of the j-th feature in the i-th observation, μ_j is its mean, and σ_j is the standard deviation of this j-th feature.

The second step is the computation of the covariance matrix:

$$Cov(X) = \frac{1}{n} X^T X \quad (2)$$

where X is the previously standardized matrix and n is the number of observations.

The third step is to calculate the eigenvalues and eigenvectors (principal components) of this matrix, which represent the amount of variance they represent and the direction in which the data varies the most. Mathematically, it can be written as:

$$Cov(X)\mathbf{v} = \lambda\mathbf{v} \quad (3)$$

Where λ represents the eigenvalue and \mathbf{v} is the eigenvector.

After calculating the eigenvalues and eigenvectors, we can select how many we would

like to use for the representation. Let's mark these selected vectors as:

$$\mathbf{V}_k = [\mathbf{v}_1 \ \mathbf{v}_2 \ \dots \ \mathbf{v}_k]$$

With these, we can construct the transformed dataset by projecting the original data onto this new basis of principal components.

$$Y = X \cdot \mathbf{V}_k \quad (4)$$

where Y is the transformed lower - dimensional dataset.

2.1.2 t-SNE

The basic idea behind t-SNE is that the similar data points in high-dimensional space should be represented as nearby points in a lower-dimensional embedding.

To understand it, we need to take a look at its predecessor, the Stochastic Neighbour Embedding (SNE)(Hinton, Roweis, 2002) [11]. The SNE performs the dimension reduction by calculating probabilities that represent similarities based on the high-dimensional Euclidean distances between the data points. This is because Euclidean distances serve as a measure of dissimilarity or similarity between points in a high-dimensional space. The conditional probability is calculated as if the data point x_i would pick the data point x_j as its neighbor based on their probability density under a Gaussian centered at x_i , meaning nearby points would have a significantly higher probability.

$$p_{j|i} = \frac{\exp(-\|x_i - x_j\|^2/2\sigma_i^2)}{\sum_{k \neq i} \exp(-\|x_i - x_k\|^2/2\sigma_i^2)} \quad (5)$$

The same can be done for two points: y_i and y_j in a lower dimension. Except we give the variance a value of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ this time, so that the Gaussian distribution will have a deviation of 1, which helps to prevent the probabilities from becoming too small or too large during the optimization process. The form of probability in this case is:

$$q_{j|i} = \frac{\exp(-\|y_i - y_j\|^2)}{\sum_{k \neq i} \exp(-\|y_i - y_k\|^2)} \quad (6)$$

To check whether the lower-dimensional distribution accurately represents the higher-dimensional distribution describing the original pairwise similarities, we use the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence. In the context of SNE, minimizing the sum of the KL divergence for all points with the help of gradient descent methods means it aligns the conditional probabilities of pairwise similarities in the high-dimensional space with those in the lower-

dimensional one. The formula for this cost function is:

$$C = \sum_i KL(P_i || Q_i) = \sum_i \sum_j p_{j|i} \log \frac{p_{j|i}}{q_{j|i}} \quad (7)$$

One big problem with the KL divergence is that it is asymmetric, meaning that $KL(P || Q)$ is generally not equal to $KL(Q || P)$, which can affect the interpretation of the results. Minimizing $KL(P || Q)$ may prioritize preserving the local structure of the original data in the embedding space, while minimizing $KL(Q || P)$ may prioritize maintaining the global structure.

According to (Van Der Maaten, Hinton, 2008)[27] the t-SNE aims to solve this problem by introducing a symmetrical version of the cost function (Cook, et al. , 2007)[3] that was used in SNE. It also uses a Student-t distribution for the probability calculation in low-dimensions. One of its advantages is that the heavy tails of the Student-t distribution make it less sensitive to outliers, ensuring that extreme pairwise similarities are not overemphasized, resulting in a more reliable representation of the data.

2.1.3 UMAP

UMAP, was introduced by McInnes et al. in their 2018 paper [17]. At its core, UMAP operates on principles rooted in the concept of manifold learning, which suggests that high-dimensional data often reside on low-dimensional manifolds embedded within the surrounding space. It takes advantage of insights from Riemannian geometry (Petersen, 2006)[21], which is a sub-discipline of differential geometry that studies curved spaces using the techniques of calculus, and provides a framework for understanding the geometric properties of spaces that are not necessarily flat. In this framework, distances, angles, and curvature are defined in terms of a metric tensor, which allows geometric quantities to be measured and relationships between points in space to be explored.

The algorithm builds a large-scale fuzzy topological representation of the entangled structure of the data manifold. With this representation, each data point is mapped in detail, and characterized by a computed degree of association with its neighbors. Thanks to this, it can capture the local and global structures of the data, providing a strong basis for dimensionality reduction.

It is also worth mentioning that UMAP optimizes an objective function that balances the preservation of local and global structure with the minimization of cross-entropy loss. Cross-entropy loss is commonly used in machine learning for classification tasks, as it quantifies the dissimilarity between predicted probabilities and actual class labels by measuring the difference between the predicted probability distribution and the true distribution of the data. Minimizing this cross-entropy loss aims to improve the model's ability to accurately

implement the classification of data points into their respective classes.

2.2 Clustering

Clustering is a common technique in data analysis and machine learning that is used to group similar data points together based on specific features or characteristics, in our case, the shape of the astrocytes. The goal is to find these inherent structures without any prior knowledge of the groups. If these patterns and relationships among the cells are identified, it could provide a strong basis for experts to analyze which mutation of the cells might lead to which disease.

One popular method for clustering is the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN). DBSCAN, as in Ester, et al., 1996[7] is a new approach to unsupervised learning that is characterized by its ability to detect clusters of arbitrary shapes in spatial data while dealing effectively with the constant challenge of noise.

DBSCAN's effectiveness lies in its adaptive nature, which avoids the need for a priori determination of the number of clusters, instead, it is dynamically learning about its structures based on data density. This feature makes it particularly suitable for exploratory data analysis, where the underlying distribution of clusters may be unknown or complex.

The operation of the algorithm involves a careful classification of data points into three distinct categories: core points, boundary points, and noise points. Core points serve as the anchors of clusters, defined by their nearness to a minimum number of neighboring points within a specified radius. These core points combine to form the nucleus of each cluster. Border points, while within the radius of a core point, do not satisfy the required density threshold and serve as transitional elements at the edge of clusters. Noise points, on the other hand, are isolated entities floating in regions without enough density to justify inclusion in a detectable cluster. DBSCAN's ability to recognize these sophisticated characteristics enables it to adapt seamlessly to data sets characterized by varying densities and complex spatial arrangements.

2.3 Evaluation

One way to evaluate detection algorithms is to use COCO metrics, which help to measure the accuracy of the detection models by comparing predicted bounding boxes to ground truth annotations. One of its metrics, the Average Precision (AP), is used for binary classification tasks, providing a measure of the model's performance with the help of:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True positives}}{\text{True positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

and

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True positives}}{\text{True positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

a precision-recall (PR) curve can be drawn up, which plots the value of precision against recall at different threshold values. By integrating the area under the PR curve, it calculates a single scalar value, which describes the model’s performance. The other metric that is frequently used is the mean Average Precision (mAP), which averages the AP across all classes under consideration:

$$\text{mAP} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_i^k AP_i \quad (8)$$

However, in medical imaging, the FROC analysis is favored over the COCO metrics due to the unique requirements of diagnosing the abnormalities within the images. As compared to typical object detection tasks, medical imaging often involves the identification of multiple lesions or anomalies, requiring a detailed evaluation of detection performance across different sizes and locations, which FROC analysis enables by estimating a sensitivity to true positives without setting fixed detection thresholds. This provides a comprehensive understanding of the algorithm’s performance, and aligns the approach with the clinical goals of medical imaging, where accurate lesion detection with minimal false positives is essential for well informed decision-making and patient care.

2.3.1 Free response Receiver Operating Characteristic

According to Bandos, et al., 2009[1], the FROC analysis (Egan, et al., 1961)[6] serves as a valuable tool in the evaluation of bioinformatic systems, particularly where the detection of abnormalities is crucial, such as in radiology or pathology.

Unlike traditional binary classification methods, one of the key aspects of FROC analysis is the placement of marks, which are essentially annotations made by the diagnostic system to indicate areas of potential abnormality. These marks are accompanied by ratings or scores, reflecting the system’s confidence or suspicion level regarding the presence of an abnormality at that location. This rating system allows for a graded evaluation of the detected abnormalities, providing more information than a simple binary classification of positive or negative.

In FROC analysis, all marks placed by the system are considered potential indicators of abnormality, regardless of their rating. This means that even low-confidence marks are taken into account during evaluation.

We use various summary indices to evaluate the performance, which can be placed into two broad categories: those that focus on ROC-like diagnostic performance and those that directly measure FROC-like diagnostic performance. ROC-type indices typically assess the system’s ability to differentiate between subjects with known abnormalities (true positives)

and those without (true negatives) by considering all marks within each examination.

On the other hand, FROC-type indices aim to directly evaluate the system's performance in placing and rating marks on abnormalities. These indices may include metrics such as the true positive fraction (TPF) at a specific false positive rate (FPR) (Chakraborty, et al. 2004)[2] or the area under the FROC curve up to a given FPR threshold (Samuelson, et al. 2006)[23].

In summary, FROC analysis offers a sophisticated approach to evaluate detection algorithms by considering the placement, rating, and classification of marks on suspected abnormalities.

To show an example of a FROC curve:

Figure 1: FROC curve of a prediction over an example dataset.

In this case, each marker represents a threshold value from 0 to 1, and as mentioned before, several different metrics like sensitivity and the average number of false positives (FP) per image can be calculated to describe the performance of the system. Analyzing this figure, it can be seen that it has high sensitivity coupled with low FP per frame, which is an indication that the model's predictions are accurate.

2.4 Detection algorithms

In the past, visual recognition tasks have relied heavily on the use of SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform)(Lowe, 2004)[16], a feature identifier that detects and describes key points in images, making these identifiers invariant to scale, rotation, and partially to

changes in illumination and viewpoint, and HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradients)(Dalal, et al., 2005)[4], which systematically computes and normalizes the gradient-oriented histograms across an image, effectively capturing edge and texture information.

It is also known that recognition in both biological and artificial vision systems occurs through a hierarchical process, where initial stages detect simple features such as edges and colors, intermediate stages identify more complex patterns, and final stages achieve high-level recognition of objects and scenes. In computer science, these multi-layered processes are represented by Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Over the years, the evolution of CNNs has shown that they can lead to much higher object recognition performance compared to systems based on simpler HOG-like features.

2.4.1 R-CNN

Some detection methods approach the localization as a regression problem, others use a sliding window detector. As introduced in Girshick, et al., 2014 [10] in the case of R-CNN, they solved the localization problem by operating within the "recognition using regions" paradigm. Hence the name R-CNN: "regions with CNN". The recognition using regions paradigm in computer vision focuses on analyzing specific regions within an image that are likely to contain objects, rather than the entire image or arbitrary fixed-size regions. This approach uses region proposal algorithms to identify these potential object-containing regions, which are then analyzed using feature extraction and classification techniques.

A R-CNN object detection system consists of three main modules. The first step is the creation of category-independent region proposals. At the time when R-CNN was proposed, one of the leading approaches to region proposal was the selective search (Uijlings, et al., 2013) [26], which combines low-level features like color, texture, and shape to generate a diverse set of region proposals. It iteratively merges similar regions into larger ones, maintaining a hierarchy of regions at different scales. This hierarchical approach allows selective search to efficiently cover the space of possible object locations, providing a wide range of candidate regions for further analysis.

In the second step, the object detection system focuses on using a large convolutional neural network (CNN) to extract fixed-length feature vectors from each proposed region. This step plays a crucial role in transforming the raw pixel data within each proposed region into a compact and informative representation that encapsulates the unique characteristics of the objects present in the region.

The CNN used in this step is typically a deep learning architecture consisting of multiple layers, including convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers.

As the CNN processes the region proposals, it applies filters to the input feature maps, capturing local patterns and spatial relationships between neighboring pixels. Through suc-

cessive layers, the network learns to extract increasingly complex features, recognizing edges, textures, shapes, and other identifying cues that indicate the presence of objects.

It is important to note that the CNN is often pre-trained on large datasets such as ImageNet (Deng, et al., 2012)[5] using techniques like supervised learning. This pre-training allows the network to acquire a deep understanding of generic visual features, which can then be fine-tuned on domain-specific datasets for object detection tasks.

The output of the CNN for each region proposal is a fixed-length feature vector that encodes the most relevant visual information present in the region. These feature vectors serve as high-level representations of the proposed regions, which are critical for the following stages of the object detection pipeline. In the third step, the object detection system employs a set of class-specific linear support vector machines (SVMs). These SVMs are trained to classify each proposed image region into one of the predefined object classes (cars, dogs, cats, etc.) that the model aims to detect.

The class-specific SVMs operate independently, evaluating the extracted feature vectors from each region proposal to determine the likelihood of the presence of their respective object classes. During training, the SVMs learn to differentiate between positive examples (regions containing instances of the target object class) and negative examples (regions containing background or other objects). This is achieved by finding an optimal decision boundary that maximizes the margin between positive and negative examples in the feature space.

Once trained, the SVM classifiers assign a confidence score or probability to each proposed region, indicating the likelihood that it contains an instance of the corresponding object class. Regions with high confidence scores are considered positive detections for the associated class, while regions with low scores are typically discarded as false positives.

By using class-specific SVMs, the R-CNN-like system can achieve multi-class object detection, enabling it to simultaneously identify and localize multiple object categories within an image.

In addition to the three primary modules of region proposal, feature extraction, and classification using SVMs, R-CNN also includes a bounding box regression inspired by (Felzenswalb, et al., 2009)[8]. This step aims to improve the accuracy of object localization by adjusting the coordinates of the region proposals to better match the actual objects present in the image.

This bounding box regression step uses the features extracted by the CNN from each proposed region. While analyzing these features, the bounding box regression model learns to predict adjustments to the coordinates of the region's bounding box, effectively refining its position and size to better encapsulate the object of interest.

During training, the bounding box regression model is trained in conjunction with the

classification SVMs to jointly optimize both tasks. This regression model learns to predict new detection windows given the pool features for a selective search region.

2.4.2 Fast R-CNN

Fast R-CNN (Girshick, 2015)[9] aims to address the computational inefficiencies of R-CNN, by streamlining the object detection process with the integration of region of interest (RoI) pooling into the convolutional neural network (CNN). This optimization significantly reduces the computational load, as the CNN only needs to be evaluated once per image.

In addition, the SVMs are replaced by a softmax layer for each object class, allowing end-to-end training of the entire detection network. These softmax functions convert the raw feature values into probabilities by normalizing them across all classes. A new RoI pooling function is also included. Unlike traditional pooling operations that operate on fixed-size regions, RoI pooling dynamically adapts to the size and aspect ratio of each proposed region, enabling faster speeds of training and improved detection accuracy compared to its predecessor.

The architecture of the Fast R-CNN best can be described by a figure from Girshick , 2015 [9]

Figure 2: Fast R-CNN architecture

2.4.3 Faster R-CNN

In Faster R-CNN (Ren, et al., 2015)[22], a region proposal network (RPN) is integrated directly into the detection pipeline, which further optimizes the region proposal process. The RPN operates convolutively over the CNN feature maps, generating region proposals by predicting objectness scores and bounding box offsets for a dense set of anchor boxes. Additionally, Faster R-CNN preserves the RoI pooling mechanism introduced in Fast R-CNN, allowing efficient feature extraction from variable-sized regions within the CNN feature maps. By leveraging the shared convolutional features between the RPN and the following stages, Faster R-CNN achieves significant speed improvements while maintaining high detection accuracy.

2.4.4 Segmentation

Segmentation plays a critical role in the processing of astrocytes, particularly in the context of understanding their morphology and its implications for healthy central nervous system (CNS) function and the development of neurological diseases. By accurately segmenting astrocytes from microscopy images, researchers can analyze various morphological features such as cell size, shape, branching patterns, and spatial organization.

Also, by gathering the segmentations of the cells, a more precise clustering could be performed.

3 Results

3.1 Dataset

To prepare the cells for clustering, some steps had to be taken. Since we work with images the first and most crucial step was to reformat them, so that they could be processed numerically. Given the huge amount of data in the dataset (Olar, et al, 2024) which contains around 8500 annotated images of scanned brain tissues with thousands of astrocytes on them, an optimal way needed to be found for their conversion.

Figure 3: Annotated image. Dataset: ALDH1L1 id: 72

The first insight was that for the dimensionally reduced visualization and clustering, we only needed the tiny images of the individual cells. The easiest way to create a new dataset from these was to cut out the bounding boxes containing the astrocytes from the original images. With the help of the ground truth files, these tiny rectangles could be located.

As it was mentioned previously, these ground truth and prediction files are stored in COCO format. COCO is a dataset created by Microsoft (Lin, et al., 2014)[15] for object detection and segmentation. It is often used in computer vision research for the training of various models. Not only the dataset itself, but also the format of its files is widely used. Typically, it has two main parts: the images and their annotations. The annotations are stored in a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format that provides key information about the images (name, path, size, id) and the annotations (category (name, id), id of the image that it is on, bounding box coordinate, segmentation mask).

To overcome the challenge created by the different sizes of the bounding boxes, the rectangles needed to be normalized based on their most important properties, their widths and heights.

With the help of histograms, the most common width and height values were identified, which tells us the common size that would best accommodate the majority of bounding boxes.

To improve the visual clarity and detectability of cellular structure, the tiny cut-out pictures were converted to the HSV (hue, saturation, value) color space, which is a cylindrical representation of colors based on the three parameters listed, and then a histogram equalization was performed on the value channel. With this step, the contrast of the images was enhanced, which helped to highlight the features of the cellular entities against the background.

To make the processing and analysis doable, the images were flattened into a one-dimensional array. These newly created representations of the images were merged into a larger array, where each row represents a distinct cell, allowing efficient access and handling of them.

In hopes of seeing clusters form, this new dataset was visualized with the help of t-SNE:

Figure 4: ALDH1L1 dataset

Figure 5: GFAP dataset

The colors on fig. 4 and fig. 5 are based on what slide they were originally cut out from. We can see some primitive cluster-like formations, but no clear conclusions can be drawn based on these two figures.

3.2 FROC

Before talking about the architecture of the FROC curve plotting function, some of its key components need to be described further.

3.2.1 The cost matrix

In the context of FROC curve creation, the function of a cost matrix is to quantify the cost of match between each prediction and the ground truths.

For this task, two different cost matrices were implemented. One was based on the Euclidean distance between the center of the prediction and the ground truth (GT) box, while the other was constructed using Intersection over Union (IoU), meaning that a score was given according to how much they overlapped with each other.

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{Area of Intersection}}{\text{Area of Union}} \quad (9)$$

3.2.2 Hungarian matching

The Hungarian Matching Algorithm, also known as the Kuhn-Munkres Algorithm (Kuhn, Harold, 1955)[14], provides a systematic and efficient solution to the challenge of optimizing assignments between two sets while minimizing total cost or maximizing total value.

The goal is to iteratively narrow a partial assignment matrix until a globally optimal solution is reached. Thanks to its flexibility, it finds application in a variety of optimization tasks like linear sum assignment, weighted bipartite matching, etc.

To reach the most optimal assignment, the following steps need to be taken:

- In the first two steps, it performs row and column reduction by subtracting the minimum value from each row in the cost matrix C to obtain a modified matrix C' , and then repeating this process for each column in C' to further refine it into C''
- Then it calculates the minimum number of lines (rows or columns) needed to cover all zeros in the double modified cost matrix C'' . These lines represent a potential assignment configuration. If the number of lines equals n (where n is the size of the cost matrix), an optimal assignment configuration is found.
- If the optimal assignment hasn't been found yet, it continues with the minimum covering, where it finds the smallest uncovered element (let it be α) in the C'' cost matrix, and subtracts it from all uncovered elements, and adds it to the elements that are covered by two lines. This step is repeated until a potential assignment configuration is identified.
- Then it creates the optimal assignment, by forming an assignment matrix X from the

position of the zeros in the modified cost matrix C'' as:

$$x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } C''_{ij} = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

If the value of $x_{ij} = 1$, it means that the i -th element is assigned to the j -th element, and if the $x_{ij} = 0$ that means that they are not matched.

The key property of the assignment matrix is that each row and each column contain at most one zero. This ensures that each element from the first set is assigned to at most one element from the second set, and vice versa, fulfilling the constraints of the assignment problem. Also, each row will have exactly one element with the value 1, indicating the assignment of an element from the first set to an element in the second set.

3.2.3 The statistics

With the help of the assignment matrix, it is possible to create a statistic about the prediction, which will be used for the creation of the curve itself:

True Positive (TP): Based on the fact that the column indices represent the GTs that have been matched to the guesses, counting how many of them are unique will tell us the number of true positive guesses.

```
1 TP = len(np.unique(col_indices))
```

code 1: Formula for TPs

False Positive (FP): As for the false positives, if we subtract the number of unique row indices (which hold how many guesses have been matched with GTs) from the total number of guesses, we get the false positives.

```
1 FP = len(guesses) - len(np.unique(row_indices))
```

code 2: Formula for FPs

False Negative (FN): To count the false negatives, the number of true positives needed to be subtracted from the number of ground truths.

```
1 FN = len(ground_truths) - TP
```

code 3: Formula for FNs

3.2.4 Implementing my own FROC curve plotting function

The first prototype was designed to work with a small amount of data, so a test dataset was created, where the "predictions" were randomly drawn up bounding boxes with randomly assigned scores. As for the ground truths (GT), four of the prediction boxes were kept, and their boundaries were varied with a small random number.

Figure 6: The small "dataset"

The FROC curve plotting function itself was created with the following steps:

1. An array of 50 points between 0 and 1 was created to represent the thresholds where the "detections" will be evaluated.
2. With the help of an auxiliary function called 'filter', it selects the prediction boxes that have a greater or equal confidence score as a given threshold value.
3. The cost matrices are created
4. The Hungarian matching assigns the pairs that will have the lowest overall cost.
5. It counts the TPs, FPs, and FNs.
6. Based on the statistics, the sensitivity and false positive/image parameters can be calculated.

Where sensitivity is defined as:

$$sensitivity = \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)} \quad (10)$$

We must stipulate that the equation will only be true if $(TP + FN) > 0$, otherwise it is just going to be 0.

7. Once the parameters are calculated for each threshold value, the FROC curve can be drawn up,

Figure 7: FROC curve of the small "dataset" with Euclidean cost

where the red numbers are the threshold values for a given point.

To check if it is working correctly, some of the points could be calculated manually. For example, the point that is assigned to the 0.6939 threshold value is at 0 sensitivity and 0 FPs/image. By looking back at the data set (Figure 6), it is easy to see that there is no bounding box that has a confidence score that high, therefore none of them is going to be selected by the filter function, which results in no false positives and zero sensitivity. To examine the other extreme case, with a threshold of zero, meaning all guesses are considered to be true. The FP/image is one because there is one more guess than GT and the sensitivity is also one, because there are no false negatives.

The other version of the function, which uses the IoU formula for the cost matrix creation, was also tested. In this case, the same steps were repeated, and we got the following result:

Figure 8: FROC curve of the small "dataset" with IoU cost

The curves were identical in both cases, which is not surprising considering the placement

of the guesses compared to the GTs.

After the first working prototype, some upgrades needed to be done. For example, the approach to calculating true positives (TP) and false positives (FP) has changed significantly. While the original method involves iterating over confidence thresholds to determine TP and FP obtained from a new linear sum assignment at every step, the updated method further optimizes this process by using the Hungarian matching only once to determine the assignment of guess boxes to ground truth boxes based on Euclidean distances or their IoU. This streamlined methodology eliminates the need to iteratively process indices obtained from linear sum assignment, theoretically improving computational efficiency, especially with larger datasets.

The same tests were performed on the updated function with the same dataset (Figure 6), and got the same results as with the old method for both the Euclidean (Figure 7) and the IoU (Figure 8) versions.

Also, it was corrected to count the statistics for large datasets correctly, and a new plotting method was introduced, which allows to plot the FROC curve with a logarithmic x axis. In some cases, it is really helpful to use this to evaluate the models, because what we are really interested in is how the model performs on the intervals where it makes really small average errors.

3.2.5 The comparison between my function and the package

To validate the correctness of both methods, a comparison was made between the two implementations to see whether they would return the same result. In both cases, the same test dataset was used, which is a demo of Detectron2 (Wu, et al., 2019)[28] and contains around 61 images of balloons with ground truths. The predictions for the test were created within the same environment using a pre-trained model.

Looking at the results (fig. 9 and fig. 10), it is clear that the curves generated by both my function and the coco-froc analysis package were strikingly similar. The consistency between the two sets of results provided a reasonable level of confidence in the validity of the methodologies employed and in the correct operation of the functions.

Despite the result of this comparison, the package has a bootstrapping feature, which makes it more useful.

The use of bootstrap resampling techniques in FROC curve generation offers significant advantages in evaluating the performance of detection algorithms. By randomly sampling with replacement from the ground truth annotations, bootstrap generates multiple subsets of the data, allowing the generation of multiple FROC curves. These curves represent the performance of the algorithm across different variations of the dataset, allowing for the unique variability and uncertainty present in a medical imaging dataset.

Figure 9: Test run on balloon dataset with package

Figure 10: Test run on balloon dataset with own function

It also quantifies the stability of the detection algorithm by providing insight into the range of potential true positives (TPs) at different thresholds.

With the help of these, we can create error bars, which are the differences between the maximum and minimum TP counts obtained from the bootstrap samples. By displaying them along the FROC curve, we can illustrate the variability in performance at different operating points. To demonstrate it, the bootstrapped version of the FROC curves (Figure 9, Figure 10)

on the same balloon dataset was created.

Figure 11: The bootstrapped FROC curve on the balloon dataset

3.3 Detection algorithms

3.3.1 Detection of cells

The framework that made it possible to set up and fine-tune these models was the Detectron 2 (Wu, et al., 2019)[28]. The Detectron 2 was developed by Facebook AI Research (FAIR) and has quickly become popular among researchers due to its unparalleled combination of performance, flexibility, and ease of use. Detectron 2 uses the PyTorch (Imambi, et al.,2021)[12] deep learning library and takes advantage of its flexibility to provide a solid foundation for implementing advanced models and algorithms. One of its key difference from the other frameworks is its modular and extensible architecture. This design allows users to easily integrate new algorithms, architectures, and datasets into their workflow.

With the help of Detectron 2, two different models were trained on the astrocyte dataset, and with these models, predictions were created on the designated test images in order to evaluate the performance of the different models with the help of the FROC curves.

The first tested configuration was a Faster R-CNN with a Res-Net 50 backbone. In the context of neural networks, the backbone refers to the core part of the network, which is responsible for feature extraction. This means that it serves as the initial processing module that takes the input data (in this case, the images) and transforms it into a hierarchical representation of features. A backbone typically consists of convolutional and pooling layers arranged in a deep architecture. A convolutional layer consists of a set of convolutional kernels, which are small matrices of weights that represent a pattern or a feature that the layer

aims to detect. During a forward pass, each filter slides across the input image, computing the dot product between its weights and the values in the region that it covers, which results in a single value in the output feature map. Each convolutional layer is going to create a different feature map, and these maps will capture more abstract and high-level features as we move deeper into the network's layers. Thanks to these layers, the subsequent layers could perform more complex tasks like classification, object detection, or segmentation.

The pooling layers are typically used after the convolutional layers, and their main goal is to reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps while retaining information to help reduce computational complexity.

The main reasons why it is worth choosing a backbone like Res-Net 50 are that it has its weights pre-trained on large datasets like ImageNet (Deng, et al., 2012)[5], also the depth of 50 layers allows it to capture intricate features and relationships in the data, which leads to superior performance.

Before evaluating the performance of this configuration, let's check whether it made the correct predictions in the first place.

Figure 12: Predictions across all confidence scores

Figure 13: Predictions with a higher confidence score than 0.5

Both of fig. 12 and fig. 13 shows the same image from the ALDH1L1/test_03557 dataset. The only difference is that fig. 12 shows predictions across all confidence scores, while fig. 13 only shows predictions that have a higher confidence score than 0.5. As we can see, it makes a lot of predictions, some of them accurate, but most of them are going to be thrown out due to their low confidence scores.

As for the performance, the datasets that are worth a look are the train datasets, as they contain significantly more images and therefore more cells than the test subsets.

Figure 14: Faster R-CNN with ResNet-50 backbone on ALDH1L1 train dataset

Figure 15: Faster R-CNN with ResNet-50 backbone on GFAP train dataset

In both cases, the performance is very similar, and precise, at 1 FP/image, the sensitivity is around 0.8, and with only 0.1 FP/image it is still 0.6. The definition of sensitivity was mentioned in equation 10.

To compare the performance of the different DCNNs, the predictions were also made with another Faster R-CNN network, but with a Res-Net 101 backbone, meaning that the depth of the network was doubled, which should theoretically lead to better detections.

Figure 16: Faster R-CNN with ResNet-101 backbone on the ALDH1L1 train dataset

Examining the inside plots, it can be seen that there is some improvement, for example,

Figure 17: Faster R-CNN with ResNet-101 backbone on the GFAP train dataset

the sensitivity exceeds 0.6 around the 0.1 FP/image value.

Overall, it is not worth using such a complex model for this purpose because the improvement in performance is minimal, while the computation time has significantly increased.

3.3.2 Segmentation of cells

The segmentation was performed with the help of the Segment Anything package (SAM) (Kirilov, et al., 2023)[13], which is similar to the previously mentioned Detectron 2, but specialized for segmentation instead of detection. With the help of a pre-trained model, the segmentation masks of the cells were collected.

To perform clustering on the segmentation masks, the data needed to be formatted accordingly. To achieve this, the segmentations were transformed into contours, then the most common length of the contours was chosen as the unit length, and finally the contours were interpolated to ensure uniformity for dimension reduction and clustering.

Figure 18: GFAP - train: dimension reduction

As it can be seen, no distinctive clusters were formed. To check it's validity, 5-5 cells were chosen and visualized from the 4 sides of the data point cloud.

Figure 19: The figure shows cells and their contours from the four sides of the data cloud. It can be seen that not all segmentations were successful. However, when they were, the cell bodies were in most cases quite similar.

Examining the images and the fact that most of the cells only have a minimal change in their bodies, it is not surprising that there are no individual clusters forming. It is also important to highlight, that the SAM package couldn't capture the branching of the cells, which could have led to a better result in terms of clustering. The same procedure was repeated for the ALDH1L1 - train dataset, but the results were similar in both cases:

Figure 20: ALDH1L1 - train: dimension reduction

To ensure that all properties of the cell morphology were examined, a second alternative method was developed for the cell representation. In this case, an ellipse was fitted to the

contour lines of the astrocytes, allowing them to be represented with their major and minor semi-axes. Since this method captures the morphology of the cells with only two parameters, it basically performs a dimension-reduced visualization, so we should be able to see the clustering by plotting the minor axes with respect to the major axes.

Figure 21: GFAP - train with ellipse representation

The same result can be seen as before, the majority of the fitted ellipses major and minor axes vary on a small scale. This statement can also be supported with the help of UMAP.

Figure 22: GFAP - train with ellipse representation

The procedure was repeated for the ALDH1L1 train dataset again, but the result showed no clustering as in fig. 21 and fig. 22

4 Summary

The thesis focused on clustering astrocytes to identify morphological variations critical to understanding their role in neurological health and disease.

Initially, it was shown that clustering the astrocytes as images couldn't capture their varying features, therefore other methods had to be implied.

To try to solve this problem, several methods for detection and segmentation were introduced and applied, but they didn't show significant improvement. What would increase the chances of highlighting differences between cells would be a more accurate model for the SAM package, that could also segment the branches of the cells, so that we could track their shape more accurately.

On the other hand, the introduction of a custom Free-Response Receiver Operating Characteristic (FROC) curve plotting function, as well as the upgrade of the coco-froc analysis package (Olar, Koroknai, 2024)[18] was a key accomplishment because it proved to be invaluable for evaluating and visualizing the performance of detection models across different confidence thresholds, and can be used for evaluation in various areas of medical imaging and object detection.

5 Acknowledgements

We thank for the support from National Research, Development and Innovation Office of Hungary through projects 2020-1.1.2-PIACI-KFI-2021-00298 and RRF-2.3.1-21-2022-00004 within the framework of the MILAB Artificial Intelligence National Laboratory.

References

- [1] Andriy I Bandos et al. “Area under the free-response ROC curve (FROC) and a related summary index”. In: *Biometrics* 65.1 (2009), pp. 247–256.
- [2] Dev P Chakraborty and Kevin S Berbaum. “Observer studies involving detection and localization: modeling, analysis, and validation”. In: *Medical physics* 31.8 (2004), pp. 2313–2330.
- [3] James Cook et al. “Visualizing Similarity Data with a Mixture of Maps”. In: *Proceedings of the Eleventh International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*. Ed. by Marina Meila and Xiaotong Shen. Vol. 2. Proceedings of Machine Learning Research. San Juan, Puerto Rico: PMLR, 21–24 Mar 2007, pp. 67–74. URL: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v2/cook07a.html>.
- [4] Navneet Dalal and Bill Triggs. “Histograms of oriented gradients for human detection”. In: *2005 IEEE computer society conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR’05)*. Vol. 1. Ieee. 2005, pp. 886–893.
- [5] Jia Deng et al. “Imagenet large scale visual recognition competition 2012 (ilsvrc2012)”. In: *See net.org/challenges/LSVRC* 41 (2012), p. 6.
- [6] James P Egan, Gordon Z Greenberg, and Arthur I Schulman. “Operating characteristics, signal detectability, and the method of free response”. In: *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 33.8 (1961), pp. 993–1007.
- [7] Martin Ester et al. “A density-based algorithm for discovering clusters in large spatial databases with noise”. In: *kdd*. Vol. 96. 34. 1996, pp. 226–231.
- [8] Pedro F Felzenszwalb et al. “Object detection with discriminatively trained part-based models”. In: *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 32.9 (2009), pp. 1627–1645.
- [9] Ross Girshick. “Fast r-cnn”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*. 2015, pp. 1440–1448.
- [10] Ross Girshick et al. “Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2014, pp. 580–587.
- [11] Geoffrey E Hinton and Sam Roweis. “Stochastic neighbor embedding”. In: *Advances in neural information processing systems* 15 (2002).
- [12] Sagar Imambi, Kolla Bhanu Prakash, and GR Kanagachidambaresan. “PyTorch”. In: *Programming with TensorFlow: Solution for Edge Computing Applications* (2021), pp. 87–104.

- [13] Alexander Kirillov et al. “Segment anything”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2023, pp. 4015–4026.
- [14] Harold W Kuhn. “The Hungarian method for the assignment problem”. In: *Naval research logistics quarterly* 2.1-2 (1955), pp. 83–97.
- [15] Tsung-Yi Lin et al. “Microsoft coco: Common objects in context”. In: *Computer Vision–ECCV 2014: 13th European Conference, Zurich, Switzerland, September 6-12, 2014, Proceedings, Part V 13*. Springer. 2014, pp. 740–755.
- [16] David G Lowe. “Distinctive image features from scale-invariant keypoints”. In: *International journal of computer vision* 60 (2004), pp. 91–110.
- [17] Leland McInnes, John Healy, and James Melville. “Umap: Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.03426* (2018).
- [18] A. Olar and B. Koroknai. *FROC analysis for COCO-like file format*. COCO FROC analysis package (0.2.15). Zenodo. May 2024. URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/11098382>.
- [19] Alex Olar et al. “Annotated dataset for training deep learning models to detect astrocytes in human brain tissue”. In: *Scientific Data* 11.1 (2024), p. 96.
- [20] Karl Pearson. “LIII. On lines and planes of closest fit to systems of points in space”. In: *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin philosophical magazine and journal of science* 2.11 (1901), pp. 559–572.
- [21] Peter Petersen. *Riemannian geometry*. Vol. 171. Springer, 2006.
- [22] Shaoqing Ren et al. “Faster r-cnn: Towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks”. In: *Advances in neural information processing systems* 28 (2015).
- [23] Frank W Samuelson and Nicholas Petrick. “Comparing image detection algorithms using resampling”. In: *3rd IEEE International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging: Nano to Macro, 2006*. IEEE. 2006, pp. 1312–1315.
- [24] Michael V Sofroniew and Harry V Vinters. “Astrocytes: biology and pathology”. In: *Acta neuropathologica* 119 (2010), pp. 7–35.
- [25] Ilida Suleymanova et al. “A deep convolutional neural network approach for astrocyte detection”. In: *Scientific reports* 8.1 (2018), p. 12878.
- [26] Jasper RR Uijlings et al. “Selective search for object recognition”. In: *International journal of computer vision* 104 (2013), pp. 154–171.
- [27] Laurens Van der Maaten and Geoffrey Hinton. “Visualizing data using t-SNE.” In: *Journal of machine learning research* 9.11 (2008).

- [28] Yuxin Wu et al. *Detectron2*. <https://github.com/facebookresearch/detectron2>. 2019.